

Stability Indicating Method Development and Validation of Simultaneous Estimation of Nivolumab and Relatlimab in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form by Using Rp-Hplc

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Abstract

A simple, specific, sensitive, rapid, precise, accurate, robust, and stability indicating reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography method has been developed for the quantitative analysis of Nivolumab and Relatlimab in pharmaceutical dosage form. Chromatographic separation of Nivolumab and Relatlimab was achieved on Waters Alliance-e2695 by using Waters Waters X-Terra RP-18 (250x 4.6mm, 5 μ) column and the mobile phase containing Acetonitrile: 0.1% Perchloric acid in the ratio of 40:60% v/v. The flow rate was 1.0 ml/min; detection was carried out by absorption at 231nm using a photodiode array detector at ambient temperature. The number of theoretical plates and tailing factor for Nivolumab and Relatlimab were NLT 2000 and should not more than 2 respectively. % Relative standard deviation of peak areas of all measurements always less than 2.0 respectively. The validation was carried out an optimized method and obtained results were within the limits of acceptance criteria for all the parameters like System suitability, Specificity, Linearity, Accuracy, Precision, LOD, LOQ, Robustness and stability of the method has been checked by the forced degradation studies. Based on the above information the method can be used for the daily routine analysis.

Keywords: RP-HPLC, Nivolumab, Relatlimab, Forced degradation studies.

Introduction

In the field of biological separation and purification, reversed phase chromatography has been used both analytically and preparatively. Reversed phase chromatography can separate hydrophobic molecules, such as proteins, peptides, and nucleic acids, with high recovery and resolution¹. Because of its wide range of applications, reversed-phase chromatography is now the most popular separation technology in HPLC. It is believed that more than 65% (perhaps up to 90%) of all HPLC separations are performed in reversed-phase mode. The reasons for this include the simplicity, versatility, and scope of the reversed-phase approach, which can handle compounds of varying polarity and molecular mass.^{2,3,4}

Relatlimab, the first produced anti-LAG-3 antibody, entered clinical trials in 2013 and has been used to treat a number of malignancies, including leukemia and melanoma. Relatlimab, an immune checkpoint inhibitor, has been tested in combination with other checkpoint inhibitors such as nivolumab due to its low efficacy when administered alone. It functions through Lymphocyte-activation gene 3 (LAG-3), also known as CD223, a type I transmembrane protein in the immunoglobulin superfamily.^{5,6}

Its expression on activated T-cells was primarily stimulated by antigen stimulation⁷, and among its many roles include the suppression of Th1 cell proliferation and the decrease in the release of cytokines in these activated T-cells, including IL-2, IFN γ , and TNF. Relatlimab is a monoclonal antibody of human IgG4 type that binds to LAG-3 and blocks its signaling pathway. This antagonistic effect stimulates the proliferation of T cells and the production of cytokines, leading to the restoration of tumor immunosurveillance. When Relatlimab is used with nivolumab, a PD1 receptor blocker, the anti-tumor effects of PD-1 inhibition are enhanced.

Nivolumab is recommended for the treatment of resectable or metastatic non-small cell lung cancer, melanoma as an adjuvant, and melanoma that is not resectable or metastatic. It primarily functioned by attaching to the PD-1 receptor on T-cells and blocking the function of these cells through the ligands PD-L1 and PD-L2. PD-L1 and PD-L2 are expressed by tumor cells.⁸ By binding to PD-1, nivolumab prevents PD-L1 and PD-L2 from suppressing T-cell activity, hence enabling the restoration of a patient's tumor-specific T-cell response.

FigNo.1 Molecular structure of Relatlimab

FigNo.2 Crystal structure of Nivolumab

Materials and Methodology

- **Instrument:** HPLC instrument used was of WATERS HPLC 2965 SYSTEM with Waters e 2695-Empower software 2.0 versions. UV-VIS spectrophotometer UV-1700. Eutech pH meter and Sartouris weighing balance for Nivolumab and Relatlimab.
- **Materials:** Nivolumab and Relatlimab, Combination of Nivolumab and Relatlimab Marketed formulation forms, Acetonitrile, Water (Milli Q) and Perchloric acid.
- **Preparation of Mobile Phase:** The mobile phase was made by combining 0.1% perchloric acid with acetonitrile in a 40:60 ratio. A 0.45 μ membrane filter was used to filter it out of any impurities that would have affected the final chromatogram.
- **Preparation of standard Stock solution:** Weigh precisely, then transfer 12 mg of Nivolumab and 4 mg of Relatlimab working standard into a 10 ml dry volumetric flask. Add diluent, sonicate to dissolve, then use the same solvent to bring the volume up to the required level. (Stock arrangement)
- **Preparation of Sample Stock Solution:** Precisely measure out 1 milliliter of Nivolumab and Relatlimab mixture, then place it into a 10 milliliter dry volumetric flask. Next, add diluent and sonicate for a maximum of 30 minutes to completely dissolve the mixture. Finally, centrifuge for another 30 minutes to ensure that the volume is adjusted using the same solvent. After that, a 0.45 micron injection filter (stock solution) is used to filter it.

Fig No. 4 Optimized chromatogram of Nivolumab and Relatlimab

Method Development: To optimize chromatographic methods, achieve symmetrical peak design, and improve resolution, a thorough examination of chromatographic settings, including column type and temperature, mobile phase, and flowing velocity, is necessary. After experimenting with several combinations of suitable solvents, the ideal mobile phase was determined to be acetonitrile 0.1% perchloric acid (40:60) at a flow rate of 1 ml/min utilizing a Waters X-Terra RP-18 (250*4.6mm,5 μ) at 231 nm.

Results and Discussion

Method Validation: Several variables were taken into account throughout the validation process of the recommended technique in compliance with the requirements of ICH Q2R1, including system suitability, linearity, accuracy, robustness, precision, and selectivity.

Linearity: The degree to which the analysis technique produces test results that scale linearly with the amount of analyte in the supplied sample is known as linearity, according to ICH. The difference between the greatest and lowest concentrations of an analyte is known as its spectrum, and it serves as a measure of the linearity, accuracy, and precision of the analytical procedure. Nivolumab (30 ppm-180 ppm) and Relatlimab (10 ppm-60 ppm) are produced in six linear concentrations and injected. Nivolumab and Relatlimab's regression equations are determined to be $y = 24470.41x + 3145.25$ and $y = 27668.86x + 2505.79$, respectively, with a regression coefficient of 0.999. A correlation coefficient was computed by comparing the calibration graph to the linear regression formula. Figures 5 and 6 showed the linearity findings.

Fig No.5 Calibration curve of Nivolumab

Fig No.6 Calibration curve of Relatlimab

Fig No.7 Linearity Chromatogram

Assay

Table No.1 Assay of Nivolumab & Relatlimab

Brand	Drug	Sample area	Avg sample area (n=2)	Std. Conc. (µg/ml)	Sample Conc. (µg/ml)	Label amount (mg)	Std purity	Amount found (µg/ml)	% assay
	Nivolumab	3068759	3071490	120	120	12	99.9	11.97	99.8
		3074221							
	Relatlimab	1043267	1054813	40	40	4	99.8	4.03	100.8

Fig No.8 Assay Chromatogram Precision

Method precision: It is a homogenous sample of single batch should be analyzed 6 times. This indicates whether a method is giving constant results for a single batch. In this analyze the sample six times and calculate the % RSD. The % RSD for retention time should not be more than 1.0, and for peak area should not be more than 2.0. In method precision the %RSD for assay of six sample solutions should not be more than 2.0

Fig No.9 chromatogram of Repeatability

Intermediate precision: Analyzed sample same batch used in method precision solutions of same sets that were prepared separately as described under method precision as per methodology by another analyst using different column different HPLC and on a different day. Signal to noise ratio from limit of quantification solution should be about 10.

Fig No.10 Interday precision chromatogram

Accuracy: Three levels of Accuracy samples were prepared by standard addition method. Triplicate injections were given for each level of accuracy and mean %Recovery was obtained as 100.2% and 100.2% for Nivolumab and Relatlimab respectively

Fig No.11 Accuracy chromatogram

LOD and LOQ: The limit of detection (LOD) limit of quantification (LOQ) of the drug carry was calculated using the following equation as per international conference harmonization (ICH) guidelines. LOD for Nivolumab, was found to be 0.36µg/mL and LOQ for Nivolumab, was found to be 1.20µg/ml, LOD for Relatlimab was found to be 0.12 µg/ml and LOQ for Relatlimab was found to be 0.40µg/ml.

LOD = 3.3 X σ /S

LOQ = 10 X σ /S

Fig No.12 LOD

Fig No.13 LOQ

Robustness: Small deliberate changes in method like Flow rate, mobile phase ratio, and temperature are made but there were no recognized change in the result and are within range as per ICH Guide lines.

Table No.2: Robustness results of Nivolumab by RP-HPLC

Parameter	Nivolumab					
	Condition	Retention time(min)	Peak area	Resolution	Tailing	Plate count
Flow rate Change (mL/min)	Less flow (0.9ml)	3.598	2962369		1.21	12522
	Actual (1ml)	3.422	3065143		1.19	12413
	More flow (1.1ml)	3.271	3231487		1.12	12347
Organic Phase change	Less Org (36:64)	3.702	2853640		1.18	12596
	Actual (40:60)	3.427	3095481		1.16	12419
	More Org (44:56)	3.123	3354324		1.09	12376

Table No.3: Robustness results of Relatlimab by RP-HPLC

Parameter	Relatlimab					
	Condition	Retention time(min)	Peak area	Resolution	Tailing	Plate count
Flow rate Change (mL/min)	Less flow (0.9ml)	5.511	984965	6.75	1.10	8779
	Actual (1ml)	5.330	1047065	6.69	1.07	8679
	More flow (1.1ml)	5.244	1131748	7.01	1.04	8561
Organic Phase change	Less Org (36:64)	5.638	857875	6.88	1.02	8734
	Actual (40:60)	5.332	1053891	6.64	1.08	8672
	More Org (44:56)	5.097	1321542	7.03	1.01	8534

Degradation data

Sample solutions were subjected to a variety of stresses in order to conduct accelerated degradation investigations. Nivolumab and Relatlimab were found to degrade under acidic, alkaline and peroxide, according to the results of degradation experiments. Chromatograms depicting degradation as a function of pH, acidity, peroxide concentration, temperature, and light intensity are presented in Figure.13-1

Table No. 4 Forced Degradation studies

Results: % Degradation results	Nivolumab					Relatlimab				
	Area	% Assay	% Deg	Purity Angle	Purity Threshold	Area	% Deg	% Assay	Purity Angle	Purity Threshold
Control	3079475	100	0	1.423	5.324	1044987	0	100	2.154	10.207
Acid	2678219	87.0	13.0	1.457	5.318	933579	10.7	89.3	2.108	10.233
Alkali	2652440	86.1	13.9	1.466	5.352	925727	11.5	88.5	2.169	10.297
Peroxide	2615711	84.9	15.1	1.498	5.369	904884	13.4	86.6	2.155	10.261
Reduction	2736232	88.8	11.2	1.452	5.325	1012789	3.1	96.9	2.147	10.277
Thermal	2991823	97.1	2.9	1.414	5.333	997344	4.6	95.4	2.126	10.231
Photolytic	3001047	97.4	2.6	1.405	5.374	1033356	1.2	98.8	2.188	10.215
Hydrolysis	2971588	96.5	3.5	1.483	5.391	1040395	0.5	99.5	2.172	10.249

Degradation chromatograms:

Figure No.14 Acid degradation chromatogram

Fig No.15 Base degradation chromatogram

Fig No.16 Peroxide degradation chromatogram

Fig No.17 Thermal degradation chromatogram

Fig No.18 uv degradation chromatogram

Fig No.19 reduction degradation chromatogram

Fig No.20 Chromatogram of Control degradation

Fig No.21 Purity Plot of Nivolumab

Fig No.22 Purity Plot of Relatlimab

Table No. 5 Summary

Parameters	Nivolumab	Relatlimab	LIMIT
Linearity Range($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	30-180 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	10-60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	
Correlation coefficient(r)	0.99953	0.99987	
Slope(m)	24470.1	27668.86	
Intercept(c)	3145.25	2505.79	
Regression equation ($Y=mx+c$)	$Y=24470.41x+3145.25$	$Y=27668.86x+2505.79$	
Assay(% mean assay)	99.8%	100.8%	90-110%
Specificity	Specific	Specific	No interference of any peak
System precision %RSD	0.40%	0.53%	NMT2.0%
Method precision %RSD	0.52%	0.61%	NMT2.0%
Accuracy %recovery	100.1%	100.2%	98-102%
Limit of detection($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.36	0.12	NMT3
Limit of quantification($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1.20	0.40	NMT10
Robustness	LF	1.21	1.10
	AF	1.19	1.07
	MF	1.12	1.04
	LO	1.18	1.02
	AO	1.16	1.08
	MO	1.09	1.01
Forced Degradation Studies			
Acid Degradation	No Interference from degradants		
Base Degradation			
Oxidation Degradation			
Humidity Degradation			

Conclusion

The developed HPLC method for the estimation of selected drugs is simple, rapid, accurate, precise, robust and economical. The mobile phase and solvents are simple to prepare and economical, reliable, sensitive and less time consuming. The sample recoveries were in good agreement with their respective label claims and they suggested non-interference of formulation recipients in the estimation and can be used in laboratories for the routine analysis of selected drug. Since the system parameters of HPLC method used for estimation of selected drugs in pure and shown satisfactory, accurate and reproducible results (without any interference of recipients) as well, it is deduced that the sample and short proposed methods be most useful for analysis purpose. The present work concluded that stability indicating assay method by RP-HPLC was simple, accurate, precise, and specific and has no interference with the placebo and degradation products. Hence these can be used for routine analysis of Nivolumab and Relatlimab

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